

A Mixed Reality Architecture for Human-Robot Collaboration

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Abstract—For a collaborative robot, being able to communicate its intentions effectively to human teammates is a key aspect to achieve a natural interaction. In this paper, we propose a software architecture enabling the human partner to visualize in advance the robot’s intended motion through a mixed-reality interface driven by a head-mounted display.

Index Terms—Mixed Reality, Human-Robot Collaboration, Software Architecture.

I. INTRODUCTION

The shift towards a human-centric industrial paradigm and the technological advancements in visual perception, control, and actuation [1], enabled the development of a new generation of robots capable of coexisting and collaborating (hence the name *cobots*) with humans in a shared and unstructured workspace. To match the fluency of human-human collaboration, where individuals infer each other’s intentions through implicit cues (e.g., gaze, posture, or gestures) [2], researchers explored new communication mediums for collaborative robots. One of the most promising solutions to this challenge is represented by Mixed Reality (MR). MR makes it possible to overlay interactive digital holograms on top of physical objects creating a virtual layer that can act as a communication channel to show the robot’s future movements before they are effectively carried out (as shown in Fig. 1).

For human-robot collaboration (HRC), MR interfaces are traditionally deployed into hand-held tablets [3] to show 3D holograms superimposed to the camera’s feed or with projectors mounted above the workspace to dynamically display 2D safety boundaries for the human co-worker [4]. These approaches, however, have inherent drawbacks: on the one hand, the former limits the user’s freedom to use hands during the collaboration, whereas the latter requires a precisely structured environment, a complex calibration and only provides the user with 2D information. A valid alternative is represented by commercial MR Head-Mounted Displays (MR-HMDs), such as the Microsoft *HoloLens* family. Being both wearable and compact, HMDs allow users to perceive the holographic scenario immersively in 3D from their perspective without requiring complex calibration procedures, while at the same time enabling hands-free collaboration with the robot. Relevant research in the field of MR-HMDs for HRC

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Fig. 1: Screenshot of the mixed reality interface seen from the user’s perspective through a head-mounted display. The holograms allow the user to see in advance what the robot will do in the immediate future during a collaborative process (in this case, an assembly task).

includes work from Rosen et al., 2019 [5], where the user can preview the intended motion of the robot’s arm and thus anticipate whether a particular trajectory will collide with a series of blocks placed in the shared environment, or work from Newbury et al., 2021 [6] where the authors proposed a system enabling the human to preview how the robotic teammate intends to perform a handover by displaying the expected grasping pose. These approaches demonstrate how the adoption of a similar MR interface improves the fluency of the interaction. However, they deal with relatively simple, repetitive tasks which require little to no teamwork. Therefore, our contribution in this work consists in the development of a general and modular software architecture that can be easily integrated into multiple collaborative scenarios (e.g., cooperative assembly) and enables the user to preview the robot’s intention and movements through the MR interface.

II. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The developed software architecture, depicted in Fig. 2, is composed of two main blocks: on the one hand, a *Unity* application running on the HMD is responsible for rendering the MR interface allowing the user to perceive the holograms superimposed to the real objects. On the other hand, the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework [7] has been used for implementing the robot’s motion planning and control. The two components are interfaced through a specific ROS-Unity

